

ViSS SSbD EVALUATION FRAMEWORK AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR BIO-BASED PLASTICS

ViSS develops sustainable, high-performance PHBV biopolymer food packaging made entirely from industrial organic residues. The project demonstrates that bio-based plastics can rival fossil-based ones in cost, safety, and functionality while being fully recyclable and biodegradable across all environments. By establishing a circular value chain from waste to packaging, ViSS advances the transition toward a plastic-free, sustainable future.

POLICY BRIEF

Background

Human activities pose major safety and sustainability challenges. These challenges must be addressed by society at different levels, from individuals to policy makers and industry, through the integration of different considerations in decision-making.^{a,b}

The Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) approach addresses these through the pre-market design of chemicals, materials, and products that deliver desired functions while minimising health, environmental, and societal impacts.

Integrating safety and sustainability into decision-making across all levels is essential, as highlighted by the UN's call for life cycle approaches and resource efficiency. SSbD emphasizes safety from the conceptual stage, using low-toxicity materials, eco-friendly processes, and designs that enable recycling or biodegradation.

The Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) framework extends traditional Life Cycle Assessment^c by including economic and social dimensions to evaluate overall sustainability.^{d,e}

Based on Joint Research Centre (JRC) guidance, the ViSS SSbD framework comprises two phases:

1. (Re)design, guided by sustainability principles.
2. Assessment, evaluating safety and sustainability across environmental, social, and economic aspects. The first ViSS SSbD assessment in 2025 identified key challenges and proposed solutions.

Challenges

1

Combine the four SSbD dimensions in a consistent evaluation process.

2

Adapt the SSbD process to the TRL of the solution. This is especially challenging at low TRLs.

3

Standardise data collection in the four SSbD dimensions.

4

Develop social and economic dimensions' assessment methods and better integrate them in the SSbD framework.

76

aspects and indicators in ViSS preliminary assessment for the four SSbD dimensions in 2025

ViSS solutions and recommendations

The ViSS project has identified solutions and made recommendations that can be applied at the EU level, such as future updates of Commission Recommendation (EU) 2022/2510 (8 December 2022) ^f and adapted national legislation.

Actively involve the value chain actors

Promote the **involvement of the concerned value chain actors in the adaptation of the framework** to the novel solution they are developing.

Promote the **involvement of the value chain actors in the safety and sustainability assessments of the solution** and listen to their feedback on the assessment methods proposed to them.

Establish a scoring method following the TRL

Define a scoring method applicable to all dimensions to ease the integration (e.g. 0 to 4 score following the performance in the different assessed indicators) in a homogeneous assessment process.

Set a timeline adapted to the expected evolution of the TRL of the novel solution: propose a reduced list of aspects and indicators to assess in the solutions at a low TRL and a larger list for higher TRLs.

Standardise social and economic dimensions

Focus on a small but representative number of aspects and indicators rather than a full list for social and economic dimensions assessment, for for low TRLs where information might be scarce

Promote the access to open databases and tools that can be freely used by the organizations that undertake social and economic assessments in the context of the SSbD to foster their popularisation.

Promote training initiatives to develop and popularise social and economic dimensions assessments.

Final considerations

ViSS project has been the opportunity to identify challenges and good practices in the application of the SSbD framework in the bio-based bioplastics sector in an evolving TRL (from beginning of the project with low TRLs to the end with higher TRLs).

To make the application of the SSbD mainstream, it is key to define a homogeneous and replicable process that integrates well the four dimensions. In addition to this, special care should be taken to support the development of social and economic dimensions assessments to level them with the safety and environmental dimensions and satisfactorily cover the four dimensions.

References

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